

Defect Characterization And Mechanical Properties of Multi-Layer Lattice Structure

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1. Research background and significance
2. Fabrication and experimental measurements
3. Geometrical reconstruction and imperfection analysis
4. Finite element modeling
5. Summary

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Environmentally adaptive structure of natural organisms - biological inspiration

Porous material : (a) sponge ; (b) bone ; (c) coral ; (d) Cuttlefish bones ;

Pine - internal section microstructure
Porous-random-one-way

Typical characteristics

Ultra-light;
microstructure;
high specific load;
random;
disorder
Porous,
non-continuous dense
solid material.

High load bearing characteristics microstructural design - imitating nature

Crystal structure

Porous properties

Periodic arrangement

Ultralight metal microarray structure

T. A. Schaedler, et al. Science. 2011

Structural compressive modulus

Structural compressive strength

Lucas R. Meza, et al. Science. 2014.

Additive manufacturing technology pushes micro-lattice design to a new level – making the best use of it

Microarray structure scale:

<math>< \mu\text{m}</math>;

Type of parent material:

metal, polymer, ceramic, etc.;

Multi-level lattice structure:

further design of microcell

dot matrix rods;

Multi-material multi-cell

hybrid structure

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Specimen
and
experimental
device

Types	Layers	length × width	height
BCC	1	50 × 50	10+2
	3		30+2
	5		50+2
	7		70+2
BCCZ	1		10+2
	3		30+2
	5		50+2
	7		70+2

Strain-stress curve and deformation mode

ϵ		Single-layer	Three-layer	Five-layer	Seven-layer
0.2	BCC				
	BCCZ				
0.4	BCC				
	BCCZ				

Energy Absorption

B
C
C

B
C
C
Z

Energy Absorption

$$U_V = \int_0^\varepsilon \sigma d\varepsilon$$

$$U_M = \frac{U_V}{\bar{\rho}}$$

$$f = \frac{\int_0^\varepsilon \sigma d\varepsilon}{\sigma_{max}}$$

$$\varepsilon_{ef} = \varepsilon | f_{max}$$

$$\sigma_m = \frac{\int_0^{\varepsilon_{ef}} \sigma d\varepsilon}{\varepsilon_{ef}}$$

$$CLE = \frac{\int_0^{\varepsilon_{ef}} \sigma d\varepsilon}{\sigma_m}$$

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Geometry reconstruction of lattice core sandwich panels based on the μ -CT tomographic images

Geometry reconstruction of typical struts and statistical analysis of cross-sectional sizes

Probability distribution of geometrical imperfections for the SLM-fabricated lattice panels

Distribution of cross-sectional diameter deviation along the length of struts

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Finite element modeling

1. As designed
2. With real geometrical imperfections
3. With the statistical average diameter
4. a random distribution model with the Gaussian function of imperfections

Comparison of compressive response between experimental and FEA results

BCC

BCCZ

Comparison of mechanical properties between experimental and FEA predicted results.

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1. Owing to the weak constrained boundary, the compressive modulus and initial crushing strength of lattice core sandwich panels with finite dimensions sharply decreased with increasing number of layers. In addition, the traditional theoretical model is not suitable to predict this behavior.
2. The geometrical size deviation of the strut between design and actual values is obvious and it varied along the axis of the strut. In contrast with the diagonal struts, the size dispersion of the vertical struts is obvious due to the influence of built direction and angle, which implies that the discrepancy in a multi-scale lattice structure is indispensable.
3. Compared with the as-designed and statistically-averaged models, the reconstruction model, originating from the μ -CT scan reconstruction, can improve the prediction accuracy. In terms of compressive modulus and initial crushing strength, the prediction results are consistent with the experimental results.
4. For a multi-layer lattice panel, the mixed damage behavior of layer-by-layer crushing and shear deformation is the major failure mode. The densification strain and crash load efficiency increased with the increasing number of layers, whereas the specific energy absorption gradually decreased due to the influence of boundary conditions and failure modes.

Thank you!